

Final Report EarthCube Resource Registry Implementation

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Summary

The project team accomplished the tasks outlined in the contract, developing EarthCube resource registry ontologies; a system of controlled vocabularies that allows user contributions; a prototype implementation of the entire resource registry submission workflow (from data entry to a search and browsing interface); and populating the registry content with 200+ manually-compiled records.

Goal

The EarthCube Registry is intended to provide geoscientists answers to questions like:

1. "How can EarthCube help me?"
2. "What tools work with the data set I need to use?"
3. "What EarthCube software components can I use to get my application working?"

The intention is a generalized registry of computational resources extending the data registry developed by [EarthCube project 418](#). The scope includes resources such as software components, semantic resources, interface definitions, and specifications, with descriptive information to facilitate evaluation for reuse and where feasible to directly connect data with services, tools, and other capabilities to facilitate working with the described resource. The registry should enable EarthCube capabilities to be registered and exposed for both science research usage and for software developers building applications to support research. Knowing what components are available is a prerequisite for reuse of existing work. Providing documentation with consistent content and vocabulary will facilitate the discovery process and evaluation of fitness for use. The registry will provide a key knowledge repository for EarthCube practice. Several key requirements have guided development:

- Modularity: system components, such as controlled vocabularies, form validations, etc. should be independently managed and updated, with minimal configuration effort. This approach is critical for a project with multiple interdependent components, each of which is undergoing rapid development.
- Automated execution: the entire resource registration workflow should run unattended as triggered by users entering resource descriptions. Manual interventions by system

administrators should be minimal (only in cases where administrators respond to user feedback, or run processes outside the scope of this project, or update the system.)

- Ease of deployment and use: no additional software or installation should be required to run or re-deploy the system.
- Re-use of available building blocks: the prototype is built from standard G-Suite components (Google Forms, Google Sheets, Google Drive, Gmail, etc.); as a result, the prototype system can be extended with Google APIs, and management of system components can be shared with other Google accounts
- All registry records receive persistent identifiers managed via EarthCube EZID account
- ECRR Ontologies (ECRRO) are managed in the ESIP Community Ontology Repository
- Users of the system can play an active role in refining ECRR controlled vocabularies and can explore related records and examples as they enter resource descriptions

ECRR Version 1 Implementation

The EarthCube Resource Registry (ECRR) Version 1 is an integrated system for populating and exploring registry content. This section first provides an overview of the system workflow, and then a more detailed description of operation and components. Figure 1 is an overview of the components in the workflow for registering new descriptions, and for accessing the registry.

Figure 1. Overview of Registry System.

- 1) A user submits information describing a new resource for use by EarthCube using a web form interface. Pick lists in the form are generated from controlled vocabularies.

- 2) When the user submits the form, a back end script generates a JSON-LD document containing the new resource registration information
- 3) The JSON-LD document is copied to a Google Drive directory for direct access via URL.
- 4) The p418 Miller process loads the JSON-LD into a MIMEO object store and generates a set of triples for loading into a triple store for rdf/SPARQL based access
- 5) The resource description is formatted for presentation using the SuAVE interface for user search and browsing of the registry content.
- 6) Users can access the system using the SuAVE interface, with SPARQL queries on the triple store, or via links to the JSON-LD documents in the Google Drive.

Detailed workflow discussion

Submission

Figure 2. Detail of Submission Workflow.

- 1) User submits a form at <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfyINCpV6Yck0lv2Ju7K3fLLO5jhijUlidLcvNm67QwXn6kqQ/viewform>
 - a) The form includes questions organized in 15 sections: 1) General Resource Information; 2) Resource Availability and Stewardship; 3) Resource Audience and Usage; 4) Related Resources and Dependencies; 5) Resource Type; 6-14) Resource type-specific questions (The form branches to pages for specific resource types); 15) Information about the form submitter.

- b) The form responses include free text, dates, or terms from a controlled vocabulary. Fields populated from a controlled vocabulary present a pick list of valid terms from the controlled vocabulary; vocabularies are managed separately (see below) and synchronized with the form as necessary.
 - c) While working through the form, users can browse controlled vocabularies, view examples of previously entered resource descriptions, or visualize the resource registry in a user interface. From the form landing page, they can submit issues to the ECRR github to report problems, bugs, and suggestions.
 - d) Controlled vocabularies are assembled in a single Google spreadsheet (https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1ykxgdeDjBzcTc1y64CuyaS2PhDuUtl_uO5AFUehwhxDs/edit#gid=0) that is accessed by the submission form. Users can suggest controlled vocabulary changes from any sheet in this spreadsheet, by clicking the “Suggest CV Changes’ button and providing a suggested term, definition, and source.
 - e) Authoritative versions of the controlled vocabularies are registered in the ESIP Community Ontology Repository (CORS) for version control, community access, and persistence. The controlled vocabularies in the Google spreadsheet are synchronized with the vocabulary managed in the ESIP Community Ontology Repository as necessary.
 - f) Once a user enters a resource description, she has an option to revise and resubmit the entry.
- 2) Once the resource description form is submitted by the user, several operations are automatically triggered and executed. These are implemented by Google Apps Script (a dialect of Javascript) attached to the target Google spreadsheet where the form writes responses. The operations are executed in the following sequence:
- a) A request to mint an ARK identifier is sent to the EZID identifier management system (<https://ezid.cdlib.org/>) at the California Digital Library. ARK (Archival Resource Key) persistent identifiers are described at (https://n2t.net/e/ark_ids.html) and have been used by 500+ organizations since 2001. Working with the new EarthCube Office at UCSD, we set up an EarthCube EZID account that allows EarthCube to generate DOI and ARK identifiers. EZID identifier management can be accessed from the workflow in two ways:
 - i) Minting new ARKs directly from a Google Apps Script (this is the default operation)
 - ii) Managing ARKs via an EZID proxy we developed (for operations that require ARK IDs as part of the request: this was used to generate ARKs for pre-built registry records). The proxy is running at https://maxim.ucsd.edu/ARK_ID.php. It accepts requests in the form https://maxim.ucsd.edu/ARK_ID.php?operation=<operation>, where <operation> can be one of 'get', 'create', 'mint', 'update', 'crupdate', or 'delete', along with the name:value pairs in the POST payload. The name:value pairs are consistent with EZID documentation at

<https://ezid.cdlib.org/doc/apidoc.html#metadata-profiles>. Depending on the operation, they may include:

- (1) Ark_Id (the fully qualified ARK Identifier to be created or retrieved);
 - (2) userid;
 - (3) password;
 - (4) shoulder (as described in ARK documentation);
 - (5) metadata (a multiline string containing the metadata.)
- b) Using the information entered through the form, and the generated ARK identifier, the system generates a JSON-LD file and a JSON-LD creation log file. In the process of generating the JSON-LD, the system retrieves URIs for controlled vocabulary terms from the spreadsheet of controlled vocabularies to match user-selected terms. The URI's are included in the JSON-LD document to provide linked data connectivity with term definitions in the ESIP COR..
- c) The JSON-LD document and a log file are generated and automatically emailed to the system administrator. Optionally, we can email these files to the user submitting the form (note: email quotas for Google services are 100 email recipients per day for a standard Gmail account and 1500 email recipients per day for a G-Suite Education account. Moving to G-Suite will let us be more liberal with email notifications. See <https://developers.google.com/apps-script/guides/services/quotas> for details.) Additional email notifications to the administrator include the content of individual submissions, and of the count of recently submitted records.

User Access

Figure 3. Providing user access to the registry

The JSON-LD document and the associated log file are used as follows:

- 3) Both files are automatically saved to an “ECRR Resources” directory on Google drive.
- 4) The JSON-LD file is added to an object store, for subsequent conversion to triples using GeoCODES’ Gleaner routine (the Gleaner component has to be done manually) and loading into an Apache Jena Fuseki triple store and SPARQL server. This process currently involves several manual steps, and will need to be refined and automated for a production system, but the current process is described here. The JSON-LD files generated from user submissions are placed in a Google Drive that is synchronized with a cloud object store in the UCSD cloud environment. The synchronization is done by an hourly cron job. The p418 Gleaner has been modified to access the UCSD cloud object store; it is run manually and generates a set of rdf triples from the JSON-LD document. After validation of the triples, they are saved back to the UCSD cloud object store in a new file in N3 format. The triples are then manually loaded into the triple store using the ‘upload file’ function in the Jena Fuseki user interface.
- 5) The ECRR workflow automatically updates a Google sheet that feeds into a user interface for browsing and searching registry records. The user interface is built using a new version of SuAVE (<http://suave.sdsc.edu>), which supports various modes of visual exploratory analysis and integrates with Jupyter notebooks. The new version extended SuAVE to additional sources of data including Google sheets. The SuAVE view of the registry is accessed at <https://tinyurl.com/y485a9rm>

User interaction

- 6) Several modes of user interaction are enabled. SuAVE enables faceted search and full-text search of ECRR content and lets users visualize distribution patterns (eg by types of resources, maturity, usage levels, science domains, or any other variables) or zoom in to specific resources and view complete metadata. In addition, it allows users to annotate resource descriptions, and share ECRR data views with others.

Registry records can be queried via SPARQL through the Apache Jena Fuseki interface, and can be accessed via URL from the Google Drive. The ark identifiers will be bound to a URL that will access the JSON-LD representation of the resource description.

Project process

The ontology for the resource registry was developed by a hybrid bottom-up and top-down approach, through a series of iterations to align bottom-up resource descriptions of existing EarthCube and other resources with ontologies developed in a top-down manner. The team started with the initial set of resource types and properties developed at the Resource Registry Workshop in March, 2018. These were compiled into a table defining the [resource types](#) and a [table defining the properties](#), their resource type domain, value range, possible ontology implementation, and schema.org serialization approach. Based on this compilation, a [test description Google workbook](#) was set up, with individual sheets for the description of each resource type. Test descriptions were created by populating the spreadsheet, collecting examples for each resource type from available EarthCube products or community resources used by EarthCube projects. 216 resource descriptions were assembled by the project team in this workbook.

To unify these resource descriptions, and visually explore them, we built scripts to gather the descriptions for analysis using the SuAVE viewer. Based on the terminology required for these descriptions, vocabularies were assembled in a bottom up process to focus on terminology that is most useful for describing the resources. Terms were compiled in a spreadsheet to review and edit, then assembled into a union sheet using python code in a Jupyter notebook. A SuAVE application was configured to read from this sheet, to help the project team visualize the current state of resource descriptions and relate them with ontologies being developed in parallel. The process of updating ontologies/controlled vocabularies, adjusting resource descriptions, and visualizing the registry content, was run in multiple iterations to help the team align the top-down and bottom-up views and tighten metadata fields and controlled vocabularies (see the Figure below).

Figure 4 Aligning Top-Down and Bottom-Up Development

The EarthCube Resource Registry Ontology (ECRRO) was assembled based on the resource types and properties that were found to be useful in compiling the test descriptions. The resource types from the original draft model became the base classes, and the properties on those classes were refined based on the test description compilation. Value ranges were established by inspecting the terms that were used ad hoc in the initial test description compilation. Where there was a great variety, free text was used as the property range; if a useful limited vocabulary could cover the necessary range of concepts, a controlled vocabulary was established. Property concepts were mapped to existing vocabularies, including schema.org, foaf, dcat, the Information Artifact Ontology (IAO), the Relations Ontology (RO) and the software ontology (SWO), where equivalent concepts could be identified that did not carry unwanted logical implications in their host ontology. Where necessary, we defined new concepts in the ECRRO.

The Wizard for DOCumenting Ontologies (WIDOCO)¹ was used to create rudimentary but standard documentation for each vocabulary and ontology created. This documentation is available from the github home page for each repository. In addition to creating or augmenting ontology metadata, Widico uses the Live OWL Documentation Environment (LODE)² to generate documentation about each term within the ontology and the Ontology Pitfall Scanner! (OOPS!) to “detect some of the most common pitfalls appearing when developing ontologies”³.

In addition to ontology/vocabulary hosting on the ESIP Community Ontology Repository (COR), a copy of the ontology/vocabulary files and documentation generated through Widico is

¹ Daniel Garijo, Jacobus Geluk, Martin Scharm, Almudena Ruiz-Iniesta, kartgk, Alfredo Serafini, ... Jodi Schneider. (2019, October 27). dgarijo/Widoco: WIDOCO 1.4.12: Big fixes and new configurations (Version v1.4.12). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3519946>

² <https://essepuntato.it/lode/>

³ <http://oops.linkeddata.es/>

available on the <https://github.com/earthcubearchitecture-ecresourcereg> site. Each ontology/vocabulary has its own repository under the earthcubearchitecture-ecresourcereg GitHub organization. The repositories are named using the abbreviation or full name for each vocabulary.

Deliverables

Resource Registry Vocabularies:

A total of 15 controlled vocabularies were developed (see Table and Fig. 2 below) to support the EarthCube Resource Registry Ontology described in the next section, as well as the ECRR submission form dropdown lists. With the exception of the Academic Disciplines Ontology, described further below, all are publicly available under CC0.

- Academic Disciplines Ontology
- Audience Types Controlled Vocabulary
- Communication Protocols Controlled Vocabulary
- Creative Commons Licenses Ontology
- Data Licenses Ontology
- Data Model Language Controlled Vocabulary
- Expected Lifetime Controlled Vocabulary
- Funding Agency Controlled Vocabulary
- Fundref Funding Agencies
- Maturity Controlled Vocabulary
- Runtime Environments Ontology
- Semantic Resource Types Vocabulary
- Software Functions Ontology
- Software Licenses Ontology
- Technical Specifications Controlled Vocabulary
- Usage Volume Controlled Vocabulary

Table 1. Vocabularies registered in ESIP Community Ontology Registry

In several cases, the expectation is that the larger community may wish to extend the ontologies/vocabularies. At this point, there is a mechanism on the submission form to allow users to suggest changes. We suggest that the specifications evaluation standing group discussed at this year's ECAM be charged with vetting such requests.

As a side note, Ruth Duerr worked with the Creative Commons organization on developing the Creative Commons Licenses Ontology which will be linked from the creativecommons.org website.

The Academic Disciplines Ontology is based on the Wikipedia entry⁴ because hierarchies of academic disciplines are highly contested. Fortunately, with the exception of circular relationships, ontologies allow multiple inheritance, so that disciplines such as biogeology can be located under both parent disciplines, biology and geology. Because of the basis in a Wikipedia entry, this ontology is licensed as CC-BY as required by Wikipedia.

The Funding Agency Controlled Vocabulary is based on a small subset of Crossrefs Funder Registry⁵ along with the Research Organization Registry⁶. Neither registry is small enough to include in a dropdown list. In fact, prior to this project the Funder Registry was not available as Linked Open Data (LOD) due to its size (more than 400,000 triples). At this point in time, however, the entire registry has been loaded into COR and is publicly available as Linked Open Data. It remains to be seen if the current funding available to maintain and operate the COR is sufficient to support what could be a substantial load given the popularity of the funder registry.

Figure 5: ECRR Controlled Vocabularies in the ESIP Community Ontology Repository

⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Outline_of_academic_disciplines

⁵ <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

⁶ <https://ror.org/>

EarthCube Resource Registry Ontology (ECRRO)

The directory structure for this ontology was initiated using the OBO Foundry's [ontology starter kit](#) with the original intent to:

1. Submit the developed ontology to the OBO Foundry for curation and access,
2. Develop an ontology that is harmonized with OBO Foundry, W3C, schema.org, and ESIP COR ontologies and conventions.

However, these long-term goals needed to be modified for this short term prototype effort. Specifically the ontology has been hosted in the ESIP COR repository along with all of the controlled vocabularies developed in order to achieve the timeline needed for this project. Submission to the OBO Foundry is subject to a review process that can be lengthy. In addition, some of the harmonization effort has been deferred to later iterations, though fundamentally harmonization paths to the entire suite of ontologies mentioned above exist.

One of the primary goals of the prototype effort was to produce schema.org representations of EC resources, while maintaining the structures and compliance with the W3C ontologies - in particular DCAT 2 and PROV-O. This goal has largely been achieved as depicted in the high level view of the main components of the ontology. The connections between the schema.org terms CreativeWork, Intangible, and Defined Term and EarthCube specializations of the DCAT Catalog Record, Dataset, and Cataloged Resource are visible.

Figure 6: Primary Classes within ECRRO

Text search database

Full-text search is currently provided through the SuAVE UI, which enables faceted search and full-text search of ECRR content and lets users visualize distribution patterns (e.g., by types of resources, maturity, usage levels, science domains, or any other variables) or zoom in to specific resources and view complete metadata (see sample queries, below). In addition, it allows users to annotate resource descriptions, and share ECRR data views with others.

RDF Triple Store processing

The Form submission places JSON-LD docs in a Google Drive folder. The Google drive is sync'ed with the SDSC Cloud object store using rclone. In order to convert to triples, Doug Fils' Gleaner is utilized, and the output is loaded into a triple store using the Apache Jena Fuseki interface. Periodically, a script will execute the synchronization of the JSON-LD output, the execution of gleaner, and the updating of the triple store.

SDSC Object Store:

Placing into the SDSC Cloud Storage enables files to have a fixed url

JSON-LD

https://object.cloud.sdsc.edu/v1/AUTH_85f46aa78936477d8e71b186269414e8/gleaner-summoned/ecrr/{clean ark id}

eg.

https://object.cloud.sdsc.edu/v1/AUTH_85f46aa78936477d8e71b186269414e8/gleaner-summoned/ecrr/ark_23942_g2500001.json

Triples:

Good Triples:

https://object.cloud.sdsc.edu/v1/AUTH_85f46aa78936477d8e71b186269414e8/gleaner-milled/rr1/ecrr_GoodTriples.nq

Bad Triples:

https://object.cloud.sdsc.edu/v1/AUTH_85f46aa78936477d8e71b186269414e8/gleaner-milled/rr1/ecrr_BadTriples.nq

SPARQL Endpoint:

<http://132.249.238.169:8080/fuseki/ecrr/query>

Sample queries

The ECRR content can be queried via SuAVE visual interface or using SPARQL against ECRR triples in the Apache Jena Fuseki triplestore.

SuAVE supports browsing and searching for resources using full text and faceted search. Views of ECRR content under different queries can be saved and shared online. Here are some

example queries (shown as saved SuAVE views over ECRR content, under a combination of facets):

- a) Find resources used in Seismology, which are already used in multiple places or are in production, and show their distribution by resource type:
http://suave2.sdsc.edu/main/file=zaslavsk_ECRR_10_20_Responses.csv&views=1110001&view=bucket&id=5db92122c1c6e464411439fd
- b) Find API resources that are related to Data Discovery and Access, and show their distribution by science domains:
http://suave2.sdsc.edu/main/file=zaslavsk_ECRR_10_20_Responses.csv&views=1110001&view=bucket&id=5db921f7c1c6e464411439fe
- c) Find resources that are used widely (> 50 adopters) in hydro-related domains (Hydrology, Chemical Hydrology, Hydrogeology, Surface Hydrology), and show them by resource type:
http://suave2.sdsc.edu/main/file=zaslavsk_ECRR_10_20_Responses.csv&views=1110001&view=bucket&id=5db924eec1c6e46441143a01

The Jena triple store provides a [SPARQL end point](#). The p418 Gleaner creates triples to be imported into the triple store for each run associated with a named graph in the triple store. The graph identifier (<<http://earthcube.org/gleaner-summoned>>) is specific to a particular gleaner batch, and can be used to bulk update or delete triples loaded in a particular batch. Here are some example queries:

1. query for the triples about a registered resource (<https://n2t.net/ark:/23942/g2800001>):

```
SELECT ?p ?o
{
  GRAPH <http://earthcube.org/gleaner-summoned> { <https://n2t.net/ark:/23942/g2800001> ?p ?o }
}
```

2. Get the name of the resource creator for a specific resource (e.g. <https://n2t.net/ark:/23942/g2600007>)

```
PREFIX ecr: <https://n2t.net/ark:/23942/>
PREFIX sdo: <http://schema.org/>
SELECT ?name ?resourceCreator
{
  GRAPH <http://earthcube.org/gleaner-summoned> {
    ecr:g2600007 sdo:name ?name.
    ecr:g2600007 sdo:creator ?o .
    ?o sdo:name ?resourceCreator
  }
}
```

3. Get the resource name and creator name for all resources of type 'Software' (uri = http://cor.esipfed.org/ont/earthcube/ECCRO_0000206):

```
PREFIX ecr: <https://n2t.net/ark:/23942/>
PREFIX sdo: <http://schema.org/>
SELECT ?name ?creatorName
{
  GRAPH <http://earthcube.org/gleaner-summoned> {
    ?s sdo:additionalType "http://cor.esipfed.org/ont/earthcube/ECCRO_0000206" .
    ?s sdo:name ?name .
    ?s sdo:creator ?o2 .
    ?o2 sdo:name ?creatorName
  }
}
```

4. Get the registration creator name and identifier for a resource based on its registry identifier:

```
PREFIX ecr: <https://n2t.net/ark:/23942/>
PREFIX sdo: <http://schema.org/>
SELECT ?name ?creatorName ?creatorIdentifier
{
    GRAPH <http://earthcube.org/gleaner-summoned> {
        ecr:g2600007 sdo:name ?name.
        ecr:g2600007 ?p ?o .
        ?o <http://schema.org/creator> ?s2 .
        ?s2 sdo:name ?creatorName .
        ?s2 sdo:identifier ?creatorIdentifier
    }
}
```

Initial population of databases

A total of 216 test descriptions were created using a Google sheet as described in the Project Process section. The script that loads data from the submission form was altered to process the test descriptions table. JSON-LD documents were loaded in a google drive, and from there processed by the p418 Gleaner and Miller to load them into the object store and the Jena/Fuseki triple store. These resource descriptions form the bulk of the content in the version 1 registry.

After reviewing the GeoCODES data entry GUI, it was decided that ECRR prototype functionality could be implemented using Google Forms and Google Apps Script. This approach was preferred because it is based on a commercial platform, provides flexible per-field validation processes, is modular, and is more easily understood and maintained than a custom code base. The user responds to a series of questions with free text or date responses, or by selecting values from a controlled vocabulary pick list. The submit button is not enabled until at least the minimum required information is provided. Required fields are resource name, description, a recommended citation for the described resource, the license that regulates reuse of the resource, a simple categorization of the resource type, and 0 to 2 additional required properties specific to the resource type. Users can revise the submitted resource description or submit additional entries. A form submission triggers Google Apps script code that implements the workflow described above.

Expose resources using Schema.org plus extensions through JSON-LD harvesting

The JSON-LD representations of the resource descriptions are accessible via URL. We have spot checked the JSON-LD documents with the Google Structured Data Testing Tool (SDTT) to

determine that the schema.org elements validate. The Google SDTT flags errors for several cases where schema.org elements are used as values for elements outside of those suggested by Google. By registering a site map listing the URLs for the resource descriptions, the Schema.org documents can be indexed by commercial search engines. Integration of sitemap generation and update into the registry submission and update workflow is a future project.

Next Steps

This section is to inform EC LC, TAC, and the project office about potential next steps and extensions envisioned by the team. These include

- Additional user testing and getting user feedback, to refine system design and implementation. In particular, the Google Forms framework was chosen because it is cost-effective for a rapid prototype, and provides a good balance of performance and manageability. However, it also has limitations (eg it does not support field nesting). Further, we may not want to be dependent on Google continued support of the current capabilities. User testing, and collective opinion of LC and TAC, should weigh in this decision.
- Simplifying the entry form. In some cases, the entry form instructs users to submit more than one information item in a single field (eg a URL, and a label for that URL). These may be difficult for inexperienced users. Further, some ECRR components require identification of query parameters (eg, for fields such as “potential actions”.) Technically, in many cases these complex form questions can be replaced by a set of sub-forms (within Google Forms), or by custom coding (outside Google Forms). User feedback on complexity of these fields under alternative data entry models will be needed to make a decision.
- The submission and access user interfaces need to be assessed by a User Interface (UI/UX) specialist to evaluate, make recommendations for improvement, and assess the resulting modifications.
- Populating the registry with additional content describing resources developed by EC projects and data facilities; then expanding the ECRR beyond the EC, to create a large-scale authoritative source describing research resources in the geosciences.
- Working with the CDF, EC Forum of Funded Projects, and project funders. These activities are needed to ensure that the ECRR model captures essential information about the different types of resources they develop, and can respond to key queries.
- User training: we envision a series of workshops introducing EarthCube members to the benefits of registering their research codes, and to the mechanics of submitting resource descriptions
- Integrating with (harvesting from) other tool registries or collections. In the course of this work, we found several independent resource registries. Typically, these registries don't provide comprehensive resource metadata as specified in the ECRR model. Integrating such descriptions into ECRR will require resource metadata augmentation.
- More comprehensive validation and cross-validation. Google Forms support per-field metadata validation instantly. More comprehensive cross-validation against previously entered resources, and duplicate checking requires custom code development. To

ensure meaningful reasoning over the content of the triple store, SHACL or similar technologies need to be implemented.

- While significant ontology development has been undertaken in this project, further development, and further integration with ESIP community ontology development, is needed. In addition, our effort needs to be aligned and cross-walked with global efforts (such as NASA, Arctic Data Committee, CERIF, OpenAIRE, euroCRIS, etc.) which tackle some of the same challenges.
- Ensuring that ontologies are harmonized across domains, e.g., to the biomedical communities, is necessary to enable transdisciplinary discovery, access, and use.
- One significant finding of the ontology development work is that work on the tooling supporting ontology development and documentation is badly needed. For example, the OBO Foundry tooling is quite advanced but is not compatible with the Widico ontology documentation wizard. Similarly the process of releasing the ontology to github with complete Widico documentation and integrating this with release in the ESIP COR is also not as straightforward as it should be. Ontology development tools such as Protege are not as straightforward to use when integrating with github as they should be.
- Demonstrating how workbench-mounted tools can be invoked and chained based on ECRR. This is one of the core purposes of the resource registry, and progress on this is needed to demonstrate the benefits of ECRR to a wide user audience.
- Productizing ECRR (automating manual steps; lights out operations, failover, recovery...). While much project effort focused on making the path from submitting resource descriptions to finding and querying them through Sparql or a user interface completely automated, this work is not complete (eg., generating triples from a collection of JSON-LD documents and loading them into a triple store with Gleaner is currently a manual process).

Summary

The project has developed several persistent resources available for wider EarthCube use:

- EarthCube resource registry ontology, registered in ESIP Community Ontology Repository
- 15 Controlled Vocabularies for resource description, registered in ESIP Community Ontology Repository
- Establishment of a URI naming authority for ark: identifiers, using the EZID system. The EarthCube Office can use the identifier minting and resolution services to assign identifiers for other EarthCube resources and products.
- EZID proxy wrapper to assist with URI registration; This will be useful for EarthCube and other EZID users
- 216 resource description records loaded into the registry
- A version 1 deployment registry system that can support documentation of resources using specified vocabularies, registration of new resources, and API access to resource descriptions. This will provide a platform to further develop applications using the registry to facilitate technology support for scientific research.

Links

- [SuAVE viewer](#) for EarthCube resources
- [Resource Registration Form](#) -- add a new resource
- [Resource Registry SPARQL endpoint](#)
- [Documentation on mapping resource descriptions](#) to the registry ontology and JSON-LD serialization. Project document with guidance on JSON-LD encoding.
- [Controlled vocabularies Google Sheet](#) (one tab for each vocabulary)
- Individual vocabularies. Each is in a separate GitHub repository. The 'Widico' links are documentation and visualization generated from the rdf serialization in the GitHub repository:
 - Academic Disciplines Ontology ([CORS](#)) ([Widico](#))
 - Audience Types Controlled Vocabulary ([CORS](#)) ([Widico](#))
 - Communication Protocols Controlled Vocabulary ([CORS](#)) ([Widico](#))
 - Creative Commons Licenses Ontology ([CORS](#)) ([Widico](#))
 - Data Licenses Ontology ([CORS](#)) ([Widico](#))
 - Data Model Language Controlled Vocabulary ([CORS](#)) ([Widico](#))
 - Expected Lifetime Controlled Vocabulary ([CORS](#)) ([Widico](#))
 - Funding Agency Controlled Vocabulary ([CORS](#)) ([Widico](#))
 - Fundref Funding Agencies ([CORS](#))
 - Maturity Controlled Vocabulary ([CORS](#)) ([Widico](#))
 - Runtime Environments Ontology ([CORS](#)) ([Widico](#))
 - Semantic Resource Types Vocabulary ([CORS](#)) ([Widico](#))
 - Software Functions Ontology ([CORS](#)) ([Widico](#))
 - Software Licenses Ontology ([CORS](#)) ([Widico](#))
 - Technical Specifications Controlled Vocabulary ([CORS](#)) ([Widico](#))
 - Usage Volume Controlled Vocabulary ([CORS](#)) ([Widico](#))

Project documents

[Project folder](#) various working and information documents used during project development

[GitHub repository for Ontology](#) The OWL source is in the src directory (ecro-edit.owl);

[GitHub repository for other project information resources](#)

UCSD Cloud Object store listing of Registry Objects ([link](#))

[Test description Google Sheets](#) -- project document used to compile resource descriptions

[Scripts for processing form input to generate JSON-LD](#)